

RASHID 3 MISSION: UAE'S LUNAR ROVER TO THE SOUTH POLE. H. Almatroushi¹, H. Almarzouqi¹, K. Badri¹, S. Els¹, H. AlAhmed², S. AlMulla¹, S. AlSuwaidi¹, M. Alzaabi¹, F. Arneodo³, M.C. De Sanctis⁴, D. Plettemeier⁵, R. Trautner⁶, C. Virmontois⁷, C. Yana⁷.

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Introduction: The Emirates Lunar Mission (ELM) program [1], led by the Mohammed Bin Rashid Space Centre (MBRSC) represents a strategic national effort to contribute to global lunar exploration through a series of lightweight, cost-effective rovers designed for diverse lunar environments. Initiated in 2019, the ELM aligns with United Arab Emirates (UAE) aspirations and growing commitment in advancing space science, robotics, and planetary exploration, fostering national capabilities and international scientific collaboration and partnerships.

Following the first Emirates Lunar Mission, Rashid 1, and the upcoming Rashid 2 mission [2], MBRSC is developing Rashid 3 [3], the third rover in the Rashid series. Rashid 3 represents a major step forward in scientific ambition, as it targets the lunar south pole, a region of high scientific interest due to indications of water ice detected by previous remote sensing missions [4]. This paper presents an overview of the Rashid 3 mission, including its development status, science objectives, and scientific instruments.

Rashid 3 Mission Development: Rashid 3 is currently in the preliminary design phase and successfully passed its System Definition Review (SDR) in 2025 - Figure 1 showcases the current rover design. The mission is planned for launch not earlier than 2029, with surface operations designed for one lunar cycle. Rashid 3 will land in the lunar south pole region, characterized by extreme illumination conditions, low temperatures, and the presence of permanently shadowed regions (PSRs). This high-priority region offers a compelling setting for scientific exploration and the collection of preparatory data for future human exploration and In Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) missions.

Building on the heritage of the Rashid rover platform, Rashid 3 incorporates enhanced scientific instrumentation tailored for water ice detection, subsurface characterization, and detailed geological investigations. The mission is optimized to operate in both illuminated and shadowed regions, including PSRs, which are believed to act as cold traps for volatiles, including water ice.

Figure 1: Rashid 3 Rover Current Design

Rashid 3 Science Objectives: The Rashid 3 mission has two primary scientific objectives mapped to two scientific investigations:

- Objective 1: Study the geographic and geological features of the lunar south pole region.
 - Investigation 1: Determine the surface surface and shallow subsurface properties and composition of the lunar south pole region.
- Objective 2: Investigate the presence of water in the lunar south pole region.
 - Investigation 2: Detect potential signs of water in the lunar south pole region.

To determine the surface properties and composition of the lunar south pole region, we aim to study the surface mineralogical composition, surface regolith grain size, surface atomic composition, and surface terramechanics

As for the water investigation, we are looking for signs of water on the surface and in the shallow subsurface as H₂O/OH ice layers, and in the subsurface as water ice pockets and H₂O/OH ice layers. The existence of water ice provides information on the history of water in our solar system and the evolution of the Moon.

Rashid 3 Scientific Instruments: Rashid 3 will carry a suite of scientific instruments, developed by national and international partners, designed to address its science objectives. The instruments include:

- Multispectral Cameras (CAM-25 and CAM-8)
- Lunar X-ray Spectrometer (LXS)
- Microscopic Camera (CAM-M)
- Material Adhesion/Abrasion Detection Experiments (MAD)
- Moon Infrared Spectrometer (MoonIS)
- Rashid Rover Permittivity Sensor Suite (RPS)
- Deep Regolith Sounder (DRS)

The selected instruments are lightweight and optimized to maximize scientific return while operating in the challenging environmental conditions of the lunar south pole.

Multispectral Cameras (CAM-25, CAM-8). The multispectral cameras [5], provided by the French Space Agency (CNES) CAM-25 has a spectral range of 660-960nm (25 bands) and spatial resolution of 2048x1024 pixels. CAM-8 has a spectral range of 550-950nm (8 bands with 8 panchromatic pixels) and a spatial resolution of 2048x2048 pixels.

Lunar X-ray Spectrometer (LXS). The LXS, provided by New York University Abu Dhabi (NYUAD), will determine the atomic composition of the lunar surface for elements at least down to atomic mass 16 amu using energy range of 0.5-25 keV to support geological interpretation and compositional mapping of the south polar region.

Microscopic Camera (CAM-M). The CAM-M, provided by MBRSC with a detector from CNES, will characterize regolith grain size distribution and surface texture. It has a spectral range of 400-750 nm.

Material Adhesion/Abrasion Detection Experiments (MAD). The MAD experiments will host material samples, provided by national and international entities, on the rover wheels to study their interaction with the lunar regolith and lunar environment, providing data relevant to mobility, material durability, and surface operations. Changes on the materials will be monitored by side-mounted RGB cameras.

Moon Infrared Spectrometer (MoonIS). The MoonIS [6], provided by the Italian Space Agency (ASI), is designed to detect surface H₂O/OH signatures (spectral bands at about 1.2, 1.5 and 2 microns) and characterize surface mineralogical composition through spectral measurements in the visible and infrared range 0.4–2.3 μm .

Rashid Rover Permittivity Sensor Suite (RPS). The RPS [7], provided by the European Space Agency (ESA), will detect the presence of water ice in the near-subsurface regolith by measuring dielectric properties to depths of up to 6 centimeters using two electrodes (small electrode 0-3 cm, and large electrode 0-6 cm). It will also measure the lunar surface temperature via an IR sensor and a contact sensor, and attempt to detect electrical charging of the surface.

Deep Regolith Sounder (DRS). The DRS [8], provided by Dresden University of Technology (TUD), will characterize the subsurface structure and composition, with a focus on identifying subsurface water

ice pockets beneath the lunar surface. DRS has a frequency range of 300 MHz to 6 GHz with a penetration depth exceeding 40m.

Conclusion: Rashid 3 represents a significant advancement in the UAE's lunar exploration program by targeting the lunar south pole with a science-focused mission. Through its dual objectives of investigating the presence of water and studying the geographic and geological features of the region, Rashid 3 will provide valuable data for lunar science, future exploration and resource utilization. Building on the heritage of Rashid 1 and Rashid 2, the mission reinforces the UAE's growing role in international planetary exploration and scientific discovery.

References:

- [1] Almatroushi, H. et al. (2025) Emirates Lunar Mission (ELM): Advancing Lunar Exploration through International Collaboration, EPSC-DPS Joint Meeting 2025.
- [2] Almatroushi, H. et al. (2025) Rashid 2 Mission: UAE's Second Mission to the Moon Surface, European Lunar Symposium 2025.
- [3] Almatroushi, H. et al. (2024) UAE's mission to the Lunar South Pole, European Lunar Symposium 2024.
- [4] Li, S. et al. (2018). Direct evidence of surface exposed water ice in the lunar polar regions, Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 115(36), 8907-8912.
- [5] Bézine, J. et al. (2025) Multispectral Cameras for Moon Rover, Proceedings Volume 13699, International Conference on Space Optics — ICSO 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.3075201>.
- [6] De Sanctis, M. C. et al. (2025) MoonIS Spectrometer on RASHID Lunar Rover, EPSC-DPS Joint Meeting 2025.
- [7] Eckert L. et al. (2025) A Rover Permittivity Sensor for In-Situ Lunar Water Ice Detection, European Lunar Symposium 2025.
- [8] Plettemeier, D. et al. (2026) Deep Regolith Sounder on UAE's Lunar Rover Mission Rashid 3, European Lunar Symposium 2026.